

INTERDISCIPLINARY CONNECTIONS OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AND METHODS OF THEIR IMPLEMENTATION IN EDUCATIONAL WORK

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Abstract. *The article examines such semantic concepts as integration and interdisciplinary connections as a means of forming a comprehensively developed specialist. Integration helps create a holistic worldview in the student. Interdisciplinary connections are an analysis of terms, meanings, facts, concepts, principles of two or more disciplines. It is these connections of educational subjects in the educational process that intensify the educational and cognitive activity of students; they introduce elements of creativity into the student's mental activity. The article reflects the interdisciplinary connections of the Russian language with other disciplines of the humanities.*

Keywords: *integration, interdisciplinary connections, theory and teaching methods.*

Introduction: Education today is aimed at the formation of an intellectually developed personality with a holistic, harmonious worldview, with an understanding of the depth of connections between the phenomena and processes of the surrounding world. In the light of modern tasks of comprehensive development of students' personality, the problem of integration and interdisciplinary connections has acquired fundamentally important, socio-pedagogical significance. To optimize and achieve maximum efficiency of the educational process, it is necessary to clearly understand the true needs of students of the 21st century, namely: –effectively convey information, thoughts and feelings to other people; take a creative approach to solving emerging problems and issues; actively interact with other people; –think critically, compare and analyze. Modern students need teaching methods and techniques that could optimize the effectiveness of the entire educational process. Today, the learning process is no longer limited to the traditional blackboard for writing down facts, dates, examples, formulas and the teacher's lecture, which are perceived as something boring, outdated and uninteresting. Thanks to developing technologies, active knowledge of the surrounding reality occurs in geometric progression [4]. Currently, whether we like it or not, we all live in an information society. At the same time, the opportunities that are now opening up are used very poorly. Our task is to “unfold” the information society towards the needs that people who live in our country have. First of all, among young people receiving education, scientists, researchers, teachers, educators. We must teach people from childhood and at all stages of the educational process not to be afraid of this information, teach them to use it, work with it and manage it correctly.

An integrated lesson is a special type of lesson that combines training in several disciplines simultaneously while teaching one topic. Integrated lessons are an effective form used to systematize knowledge. The purpose of an integrated lesson is to give students comprehensive knowledge about the subject of study, its holistic picture. An integrated lesson has a psychological advantage, stimulates interest in the subject, relieves tension, thereby ensuring the formation of

students' creative abilities, as it allows them to contribute not only to educational, but also research activities. Informatization of education and science is part of a global process. Information and communication technologies are recognized throughout the world as key technologies of the 21st century, which for the coming decades will be the key to the economic growth of the state and the main engine of scientific and technological progress. Information technologies make it possible to radically change the organization of the learning process for students, shaping their systems thinking, as well as to use computers to individualize the educational process and turn to fundamentally new cognitive means [5].

Integration between academic subjects does not deny the subject system, but, on the contrary, improves it and allows for deepening the interdependence between different disciplines. In the methodological, psychological and pedagogical literature, the following elements of integration are distinguished:

- 1) intra-subject connections - synthesis of concepts within a separate academic subject;
- 2) interdisciplinary connections - the combination of facts, concepts, principles of two or more disciplines.

It is also necessary to outline the features of the selection of content during integration - the integration of material from traditional, classical subjects and the inclusion of new content material for the school in the integration. At the crossroads of these approaches, there may be different results:

- a) the emergence of completely new subjects (courses);
- b) development of new special courses that update the content within one or more subjects;
- c) creating separate blocks of lessons that combine material from one or a number of subjects that exist in parallel with the lessons of the curriculum;
- d) conducting one-time integrative lessons.

Integrated lessons are an effective form used to systematize knowledge in modern educational institutions, since these lessons will synthesize the knowledge of various academic disciplines. As a result of this, a new quality is formed, which is an inextricable whole, achieved by a wide and in-depth interpenetration of this knowledge.

The purpose of an integrated lesson is to give students comprehensive (in-depth and expanded) knowledge about the subject of study, its holistic picture. An integrated lesson has a psychological advantage: it awakens interest in the subject, relieves tension, uncertainty, helps the conscious assimilation of details, facts, details, thereby ensuring the formation of students' creative abilities, as it allows them to contribute not only educational, but also research activities. The concepts of "integration" and "interdisciplinary connections" cannot be considered synonyms, since their connections are built according to the "whole-part" scheme and the latter is an organic component of the former. Interdisciplinary connections in the learning process act as a significant contributor to the activation of educational and cognitive activity of students.

Conclusion: Research by psychologists shows that interdisciplinary connections at the initial stages of their inclusion in the cognitive activity of students play the role of a situational or triggering stimulus. When solving interdisciplinary cognitive problems, the student directs his activity either to the search for unknown relationships in which known subject knowledge is located, or to the formation of new concepts based on established specific interdisciplinary connections.

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